

Pathogen-inspired peptide macrocycles as STAT1 antagonists. ANM_PA_01

Version 0

Description

The DMP outlines the various kinds of data that will be generated in the project *Pathogen-inspired peptide macrocycles as STAT1 antagonists* and describes how the data is collected, stored and made accessible.

Funder

Central Finance and
Contracting Agency

Grant

Pathogen-inspired peptide
macrocycles as STAT1
antagonists.

Researchers

Teodors Pantelejevs (orcid:0000-0003-2220-6379)

Organizations

Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Pathogen-inspired peptide macrocycles as STAT1 antagonists.
ANM_PA_01

Description:

The DMP outlines the various kinds of data that will be generated in the project *Pathogen-inspired peptide macrocycles as STAT1 antagonists* and describes how the data is collected, stored and made accessible.

Researchers:

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Organizations:

Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis

Contact: Teodors Pantelejevs

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Central Finance and Contracting Agency

Grants: Pathogen-inspired peptide macrocycles as STAT1 antagonists.

Project:

3. License

License:

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

X-ray crystallographic diffraction data

This data includes the processed structure factors for diffraction images collected on protein crystals relevant to the project, as well as the refined structural models.

The data will be deposited on the protein data bank (PDB, <https://www.rcsb.org/>). Data will be made accessible together with a pre-print manuscript pertinent to the project results.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data is generated to elucidated the structural level of the biomolecular system being studied. In the connect of the project, this involves determining the structure of STAT1 in complex with designed peptides. The data improves our understanding of how biological molecules interact.

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

txt

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

It is impossible to re use previous data sets, as the project generates completely novel data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Other scientists investigating peptide drugs.

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

PDBx/mmCIF (Protein Data Bank Exchange Dictionary and the Macromolecular Crystallographic Information Framework)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until publication of manuscript pre-print.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Protein Data Bank in Europe

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Structure visualisation software, such as coot, ChimeraX or pymol.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?
Indicate the license planned to use

CC0 1.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Open access fees for the relevant manuscript will be covered by the project budget.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Teodors Pantelejevs (orcid:0000-0003-2220-6379)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

PDB uses a password system.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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